

Empirical Cloud Mask Algorithm (ECMA): A robust multi-spectral approach for cloud detection in optical remote sensing imagery

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Abstract

Cloud masking is a critical first step in optical satellite image processing; however, many operational cloud-masking techniques rely on fixed or scene-dependent thresholds, ancillary atmospheric corrections, or complex decision trees, which can reduce robustness and transferability across varying illumination and surface conditions. This study presents the Empirical Cloud Mask Algorithm (ECMA), a threshold-free, daytime cloud detection method based on a single multi-spectral formulation using seven Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) bands (469, 555, 645, 859, and 2130 nm; 11 and 12 μm). The ECMA integrates linear and nonlinear spectral relationships into a unified empirical expression that classifies each pixel in a MODIS scene as cloudy or clear based solely on the sign of the computed value; positive for cloudy otherwise cloud-free. The algorithm operates directly on at-sensor Rayleigh-corrected reflectance at 1 km spatial resolution and does not require additional atmospheric correction. ECMA performance was evaluated against the standard MODIS Cloud Mask (MCM) for the Terra satellite product (MOD35) and the corresponding Aqua product (MYD35). Under conditions with minimal aerosol loading and negligible sun-glint, the ECMA results achieved agreement levels of approximately 70–80% with the MCM datasets. While the current implementation does not distinguish clouds from snow- or ice-covered surfaces, the results demonstrate that the ECMA provides a useful alternative for cloud masking applications, with competitive performance and reduced algorithmic complexity.

1. Introduction

The accurate discrimination of clouds in a scene acquired from passive optical remote sensing is a significant prerequisite for producing qualitative oceanographic and terrestrial data. Therefore, researchers have been actively developing effective cloud detection and masking methodologies and techniques.

The spectral mixing of different optical and thermal properties such as brightness, color, elevation and temperature is one of the approaches whose outcomes are compared to the thresholds derived from previous observations using a fuzzy logic system (Mao et al., 2015). These thresholds are assigned confidence test values to each pixel in a scene, corresponding to varied degrees of clear sky: confident clear, probably clear, probably cloudy, or cloudy (Platnick et al., 2003). This approach was used to generate the global cloud mask products MOD35 and MYD35

from the data obtained by the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) (Qiu et al., 2020). The Function of Mask (Fmask) algorithm is a refined approach that applies a spectral mixture-based methodology to imagery acquired by the Landsat-8 platform (Zhu et al., 2015). Subsequent extensions of this framework include the multi-Temporal masking algorithm (Tmask) (Zhu and Woodcock, 2014) and the Cirrus cloud masking algorithm (Cmask) (Qiu et al., 2020).

However, static thresholds are sometimes prone to problematic results as they depend on several factors, such as surface type and temperature, atmospheric humidity, and viewing geometry (Xu et al., 2024; Ackerman et al., 2008). For example, the areas affected by significant haze events and heavy aerosol load, clouds tend to be overestimated (Brennan et al., 2005; Meerkötter, 2004). To overcome these problems, temporal data

have been used to derive seasonally dynamic thresholds (Bian et al., 2014; Xiong et al., 2020; Lee and Choi, 2021).

The differences between the blue (446 nm) and near-infrared (866 nm) reflectance channels assigned to the Multi-angle Imaging SpectroRadiometer (MISR) as a function of angular viewing, was examined by Di Girolamo and Wilson (2003). The study has demonstrated its potential for cloud detection by tuning an appropriate threshold, particularly over snow/ice and desert regions that with higher land surface reflectance.

Shape recognition techniques and textural feature identifiers have also been employed to detect clouds (Marais et al., 2011; Li et al., 2017). They employ deep neural network tools, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to perform image segmentation techniques on multi-temporal reference images selected as training datasets (Zhang et al., 2022; Dröner et al., 2018; Du et al., 2019).

Among the challenges encountered by this methodology are the missing of temporal data; and the inconsistency that may exist within them, due for example, observation parallax over data collected from geostationary satellites (Guo et al., 2024; Bielinski, 2020; Yang et al., 2023). To address some of these inadequacies, Gao and Du (2025) suggested models based on the U-Net architecture, such as the Multi-Scale Dilated Attention (MSDA) module to enhance the detection clouds of varying sizes. Additionally, a Multi-Head Self-Attention (MHSA) mechanism to improve the model's capacity for distinguishing thin clouds from surface features. Machine learning (ML) strategies were also proposed to develop high-precision cloud detection algorithms by combining both active and passive data to overcome, for example, problematic night mode observations (Yang et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2020).

Polarimetric multiangular data provided by satellite remote sensing instruments, such as the Polarization and Directionality of Earth's Reflectance (POLDER), have introduced a set of new algorithms and procedures that are useful for cloud detection and masking operations (Buriez et al., 1997; Bréon and Colzy, 1999; Desmons et al., 2017). The accuracy of cloud detection in data

delivered by the Polarization & Anisotropy of Reflectances for Atmospheric Sciences coupled with Observations from a Lidar) (PARASOL) was further enhanced when combined with multi-spectral dynamic thresholds statistically derived from temporally and spatially different atmospheric models (Li et al., 2019).

The objective of this investigation is to introduce a reliable empirical cloud-masking approach grounded in a dynamic spectral band mixing strategy. The intent is to mitigate prevailing challenges and misclassifications inherent in extant day-only cloud-masking algorithms. Notably, the proposed method seeks to alleviate uncertainties stemming from dependency on static thresholds, often derived from training datasets or radiative transfer principles. Formulated, subsequently, in simple linear operations (differences and ratios), to address a dynamic and heterogeneous phenomenon, like cloud detection or masking. The proposed methodology affords data analysts operating on MODIS and MODIS-like optical satellite information the capability to devise an efficient cloud-masking strategy in near real-time settings, while minimizing processing runtime and employing the least number of spectral channels, meteorological data, and ancillary data.

Over the course of two decades, the algorithm underwent development, involving a recurring cognitive process of human learning and decision-making. This process relied on visual interpretation and was applied to about 5000 natural-color composites of MODIS images. The dataset exhibited temporal and spatial variability, encompassing diverse environmental and illumination conditions. The Empirical Cloud Mask Algorithm (ECMA) was developed based on a foundational framework comprising both linear and nonlinear mathematical identities. When the algorithm yields a positive outcome, a pixel is classified as cloudy and assigned a value of "1"; otherwise, a value of "0" is assigned, denoting a cloud-free condition. Following this logical processing, the algorithm becomes ready for execution in any compatible remote sensing package.

2. Materials and Methods

The current configuration of the ECMA, notwithstanding its inherent complexity, is designed to inclusively identify all types of clouds within a MODIS day-light scene, regardless of diverse conditions. These conditions encompass varying degrees of reflection and transparency, multi-color aerosols and densities, heterogeneous altitude scales across different land cover types, and water conditions.

The expression for the ECMA is

$$ECMA = G_i \cdot G_{ii} + D > 0 \begin{cases} \text{true (cloudy)} \\ \text{false (cloud - free)} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where

$$G_i = e^{\left(\frac{BT_{12}^2}{\tan(1 + \max(-1, \Delta BT) \cdot \min(R_{645}, R_{2130}))} + A_i \frac{BT_{12}}{R_{2130}} + A_{ii} \right)}$$

$$G_{ii} = \left(A_{iii} + e^{\max(R_{469}, R_{555}) - \min(R_{859}, R_{2130})} - \right.$$

$$\left. \frac{\min(R_{469}, \max(R_{555}, R_{859}))}{R_{555}} \right) e^{BT_{12}}$$

$$D = (x)^{\text{sign}(1+c_{ii}+c_{iii})} + \log_{10}(x) + \log_{10}(x) A_{iv}^{\text{sign}(c_i+c_{iii})} \\ - \tan(1 \\ + \min(-1, \Delta BT \\ - R_{2130}) \cdot \max(R_{645}, R_{2130}))$$

And

$$\Delta BT = BT_{12} - BT_{11}$$

$$x = \frac{R_{469}}{R_{555}}$$

$$A_i = e^{\left(\frac{\min(c_i, c_{ii})}{e} + c_{iii} \right)}$$

$$A_{ii} = \frac{\log(\min(R_{645}, \min(R_{555}, R_{469})))}{R_{2130}}$$

$$A_{iii} = \log_{10}(x \cdot c_{iv})$$

$$A_{iv} = \left(\frac{R_{2130} e^{\max(1, -\Delta BT)} - R_{469} - R_{555}}{e^{R_{2130}}} \right)$$

$$c_i = \text{sign}(R_{555} - R_{469})$$

$$c_{ii} = \text{sign}(R_{859} - R_{645})$$

$$c_{iii} = \text{sign} \left(\min(BT_{12}, \frac{1}{R_{555}}) \cdot R_{859} - \min(BT_{11}, \frac{1}{R_{859}}) \cdot R_{2130} \right)$$

$$c_{iv} = \text{sign}(R_{469} - \Delta BT)$$

Table 1 shows the details of the 7 spectral bands selected from 36 operating channels available within the MODIS instrument that have been implemented in the ECMA.

The ECMA uses at-sensor Rayleigh-corrected reflectance (R) values at six reflective solar bands, in addition to two thermal emissive bands (BT) embedded within a MODIS Level-2 (L2) processing file. The L2 files were generated using Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-View Sensor (SeaWiFS) Data Analysis System (SeaDAS). SeaDAS is an open-source software package distributed by NASA for processing, analysis, and display of ocean remote sensing data from a variety of spaceborne multispectral radiometers.

MODIS Band No.	Centre Wavelength	Spatial Resolution	Representation in ECMA
1	645 nm	250 m	R ₆₄₅
2	859 nm	250 m	R ₈₅₉
3	469 nm	500 m	R ₄₆₉
4	555 nm	500 m	R ₅₅₅
7	2130 nm	500 m	R ₂₁₃₀
31	11 μm	1-km	BT ₁₁
32	12 μm	1-km	BT ₁₂

Table 1. The MODIS spectral bands that are used in the ECMA. The bands are aggregated to 1-km resolution.

For this study, the conventional MODIS Cloud Mask (MCM) datasets were selected as reference data for the corresponding ECMA test results. The latest MCM data files were created from the 6.1 Collection and downloaded from The Earth Science Data Systems (ESDS) Program. The files are sourced from the Terra satellite data (MOD35) and the Aqua satellite data (MYD35). The detection quality of their outputs is classified into four categories based on their assigned probabilities: confidently clear, probably clear, uncertain clear, and confidently cloudy (Ackerman et al., 2008). The first and last detection pixel outcomes were used as benchmarks to gauge the accuracy of the corresponding ECMA test results using a (2×2) Contingency Table (CT) over the entire scene.

Furthermore, MODIS has a large viewing swath (width of 2330 km), capturing images of the Earth's surface under various land, sea, and atmospheric conditions and over three spatial resolutions: 250 m, 500 m, and 1000 m (Ackerman et al., 2008). Overall, the MCM provides adequate temporal and spatial reference data for an acceptable validation process. This

information includes a range of atmospheric conditions present in various topographical features. For example, arid lands are exposed to different loads of aerosols (dust), densely vegetated land cover, and water bodies affected by different levels of sun-glint mixed with or without variable dust, haze, and fires (see map in Figure 1).

The data files used in this research were spatially resampled to a resolution of 1 km, including true-color reference images, which were composited from the red, green, and blue (RGB) channels corresponding to MODIS band numbers 1 (645 nm), 4 (555 nm), and 3 (469 nm), respectively. Figure 2 displays the corresponding RGB images of the data files in Fig. 1, with a highlight of common environmental features over land (haze and dust) and water (solar-glitter and aerosols).

Figure 1 A global map showing a subset of the swaths of each dataset used in this paper: Area name, geo graphic position (latitude longitude) of the centered point in each scene, satellite name, date, and overpass start time (UTC): (1) Yellow Sea, N37° 38' 20" E121° 35' 01", Aqua 09 October 2013 at 05:02. (2) Arabian Sea, N17° 01' 38" E59° 50' 38", Aqua 18 June 2008 at 09:23. (3) Arabian Sea, N24° 17' 45" E57° 57' 43", Terra 21 December 2011 at 06:56. (4) Gulf of Oman, N24° 17' 45" E57° 57' 43", Terra 27 April 2015 at 06:42. (5) Philippine Sea, N24° 52' 35" E134° 40' 44", Aqua 05 May 2012 at 04:20. (6) Baltic Sea, N59° 33' 46" E21° 35' 55", Terra 02 August 2002 at 09:37. (7) Australia, S28° 17' 36" E156° 48' 37", Aqua 23 October 2002 at 03:25

Figure 2. The RGB datasets correspond to swaths 1, 4, 5, 3, and 2 in Fig. 1 respectively. Distinct phenomena highlighted are: (a) sub-zero clouds (boxed) and haze layer (circled); (b) sun-glint (circled) and faint clouds (boxed); (c) extreme sun-glint; (d) white-colored dust (circled); and (e) iron-based dust (circled).

The ECMA is principally structured around three core components: defined by the terms G_i , G_{ii} , and D which are explicitly formulated within eq. 1.

The prime functionality of the product $G_i \times G_{ii}$ is to suppress solar glint, recognized as one of the most challenging sources of error in a cloud masking operation, while concurrently mitigating the influence of specific aerosol types including haze and smoke from biomass burning. This suppression is achieved without compromising the integrity of cloud signals that may manifest within these phenomena.

Conversely, the D component is designed to enhance the discrimination of cloud features co-located with optically dense, iron-rich aerosol layers over aquatic surfaces, and to rectify potential misclassifications occurring at land–water boundaries, including transitional intertidal zones.

The remaining corrective factors and parameters integrated into the ECMA are responsible for refining the final output by clearing any residual sources of misclassification. These classifications correspond to grey and white tones, respectively, in the associated cloud mask imagery presented throughout this paper.

3. Discussion

The function and operational behavior of each designated component within the ECMA framework will be systematically described in terms of its capacity to either identify true cloud signatures or omit a well-defined false positive.

The G_i term in Eq.1 aims to discern the spatial homogeneity of diverse albedo targets. This is achieved through an exponential combination of the brightness temperature at $12\ \mu\text{m}$ (BT_{12}) and the SWIR reflectance at $2.13\ \mu\text{m}$ (R_{2130}). Over glint-free dark water regions, R_{2130} exhibits arithmetic underflow due to pronounced absorption, in contrast to elevated reflectance within glint-affected zones. Conversely, a squared term of BT_{12} tends to saturate—producing an overflow response—over arid, cloud-free desert surfaces or dust-affected atmospheres.

Sun-glint-exposed waters present a significant challenge for most cloud-masking algorithms, which often struggle to effectively suppress their influence. According to Cox and Munk (1956), sun-glint exhibits a wide range of profiles due to the specular nature of reflection at the air–water interface, governed by solar geometry, surface roughness, and sensor viewing angle. They have modeled a statistical Gaussian distribution incorporating an exponential term to characterize the distribution of ocean surface slopes and thereby quantify the sun-glint effect.

The G_{ii} term in Eq.1 operates in a manner complementary to that of G_i . Its primary objective is to suppress the core regions of intense sun-glint by inducing an overflow response, while simultaneously preserving valid cloud signatures located within the peripheral zones surrounding the glint-affected area.

The base in the G_{ii} term comprises of two fundamental parts: a linear term and an exponential term. Collectively, these are designed to preserve cloud-related radiometric signatures over high-reflectance terrestrial surfaces—such as arid regions co-located with similarly bright aerosols—and over optically bright aquatic surfaces affected by sun glint.

The linear term of G_{ii} is not allocated to unity; instead, it is defined as a ratio involving three spectral bands; the visible blue (R_{469}), the visible green (R_{555}) and the near-infrared (NIR) (R_{859}). The R_{859} band serves as a marker to differentiate between land from water. The second exponential term effectively aligns itself with the concept theorized by Cox and Munk (1956) for sun glint. It encapsulates the positive differences between the maximum visible reflectance over clouds due to scattering and the minimum SWIR/NIR reflectance over water, attributed to strong absorption. Ultimately, the base of the G_{ii} term yields negative values exclusively at pixels affected by sun glint, as the contribution from the exponential component is lower in magnitude than that of the linear term under such conditions. Since the G_{ii} term is exponentiated by a large factor defined by $\exp(BT_{12})$, it is driven toward arithmetic underflow over cloud-free regions affected by sun glint, thereby effectively suppressing their contribution through masking. The final product between the terms G_i and G_{ii} , effectively manages to overcome the sun glint interference, one of the most persistent

challenges in cloud-masking applications—while preserving high-albedo cloud features within MODIS imagery. Figure 3 depicts a typical baseline implementation of the ECMA, wherein

the parameters are assigned as follows: $A_i=1$, $A_{ii}=0$, $A_{iii}=0$ and $D=1$.

Figure 3. The ECMA outputs (a–e) corresponding to the datasets and their highlights labeled (a–e) in Fig. 2 wherein the parameters are assigned as follows: $A_i=1$, $A_{ii}=0$, $A_{iii}=0$ and $D=1$

The subsequent discussion will detail the specific structure and functional role of each remaining component within the ECMA framework, towards achieving a more refined and accurate cloud-masking outcome.

The A_i factor within the G_i (Eq.1) is an exponential term comprising three dynamic number generators c_i , c_{ii} and c_{iii} . Among these, c_{iii} is the most intricate and foundational, as it integrates information across all spectral domains, including the visible, SWIR, NIR, and thermal bands. It was derived following a comprehensive series of experimental testing and exhaustive iterative refinement, designed to systematically scan across all targets and produce a discrete sign outcome: -1 , 0 and 1 . Each assigned value encapsulates the target’s overall spectral characteristics, including reflectance (scattering), absorption, and emissivity. After which the output is adjusted accordingly

by another dynamic number defined as the maximum sign derived from either the c_i or c_{ii} coefficients. Finally, an exponential function of the aggregated sum is computed to dynamically suppress moderately bright peripheral false detections, including sun-glint margins, smoke from biomass burning, and haze layers.

The A_i model within the G_i term shares a conceptual similarity, albeit with differences in its mathematical formulation, to the high cloud-screening parameter denoted as “P” introduced by Roskovensky and Liou (2003). The approach also bears resemblance to the methodology employed in the MCM algorithm, wherein sea surface temperature (SST) is utilized in conjunction with visible and NIR reflectance data. As noted by Ackerman et al. (2008): this strategy is designed to resolve ambiguities that arises between the detection of bright clouds

and similarly radiant ocean surfaces on one hand and the identification of warm clouds occurring above warm oceanic regions on the other hand.

The A_{ii} term is another factor within the G_i , whose purpose is to function as a turbidity index introduced to compensate for incomplete absorption of R_{2130} over unobstructed turbid aquatic entities, and to avert misclassifying them as clouds in the ECMA framework. Turbidity, suspended sediments or elevated chlorophyll concentrations at the bottom of shallow waters, induce a significant increase in backscatter across all visible bands R_{469} , R_{555} and R_{645} . Over clear waters, the A_i factor (A_{ii_clear}) attains substantially negative values, due to the minimal reflectance term within A_i , which results in a large negative logarithm normalized by a small denominator. In contrast, over turbid water, the A_{ii} values (A_{ii_turbid}) increase relative to those over clear water, resulting in having ($A_{ii_turbid} < A_{ii_clear}$).

The A_{iii} term within G_{ii} (Eq.1) is designed to eliminate a known source of false cloud detection associated with transitional vegetation zones, where soil coverage shifts from sparse to dense. In these regions, characterized by a higher green

reflectance compared to blue ($R_{555} > R_{469}$), a nonlinear logarithmic transformation of this ratio ($x = \frac{R_{469}}{R_{555}}$) is incorporated into A_{iii} to serve as a subtractive corrective factor. However, this corrective adjustment may not hold in scenarios where a non-iron-based, white-colored aerosol layer overlies different surfaces. Those white-colored dust particles originate from dry marshes or playa regions (ephemeral lakes), whose composition can be carbonates, bleached quartz, or evaporite minerals instead of common iron-rich sands (Baddock et al., 2009). This necessitated the assimilation of relatively diminutive thermal disparities (ΔBT), whose positive gradient is often observed over deserts and can be attributed to the presence of dust storms (Ackerman et al., 2008). Within A_{iii} , the sign (polarity) of ΔBT has been adopted in lieu of its magnitude and is inverted to a negative value to suppress those misclassification errors attributed to such aerosol plumes. This strategy, however, diminished the data emanating from extreme cold clouds. To counter it, the thermal gradient was adjusted by incorporating the visible blue band R_{469} . Figure 4 illustrates the resultant ECMA following the inclusion of the factors stipulated by the ECMA A_i , A_{ii} and A_{iii} while maintaining the parameter D at unity ($D=1$).

Figure 4. The ECMA outputs (a–e) corresponding to the datasets and their highlights labeled (a–e) in Fig. 2. The ECMA parameters A_i , A_{ii} and A_{iii} are set at their designated identities while keeping $D=1$

The D coefficient (Eq.1) plays a pivotal role in detecting cloud signals mainly over water with its values bounded between the values zero and one. Mitigating in the process all misclassification triggered by diverse visible and thermal responses, particularly those caused by mineral-based dust over aquatic regions. Detecting clouds amidst varying aerosol concentrations and smoke layers presents significant challenges.

As recognized by the MCM team, smoke from forest fires, dust storms over desert regions, and other aerosol types are frequently misclassified as clouds (Ackerman et al., 2008). Figure 5 shows the ECMA obtained after assigning the power coefficient to x and A_{iv} to unity.

Figure 5. The ECMA outputs (a–e) corresponding to the datasets and their highlights labeled (a–e) in Fig. 2. The power coefficient to x and A_{iv} in the ECMA are set to unity

The power term to x endeavors to eliminate the influence of fine dust particles interspersed with clouds over terrestrial surfaces. While the primary function of A_{iv} is to reinstate delicate, feather-like cloud patterns akin to those enclosed within a top square box in Fig. 4 (b), that might have been inadvertently removed during the exclusion of dust owing to the heightened sensitivity of the trigonometric component (Fig. 5 (b)).

The coefficients c_i , c_{ii} , and c_{iii} operate synergistically to prevent masking extreme environmental elements, such as haze, dust and sun glint over different terrestrial and aquatic terrains, while

simultaneously facilitating the accurate detection of clouds existing in the proximity to these features.

Finally, the utilization of the $\max(-1, \Delta BT)$ in G_i and the $\min(-1, \Delta BT)$ in D to enhance the edge detection of low altitude thin and faint clouds over water and over land. This configuration has demonstrated notable efficacy as a viable alternative to a simplistic subtraction, due to the substantial disparities that arise in brightness temperature between BT_{12} and BT_{11} . This methodology has proven to be a critical factor for the accurate discrimination of clouds from radiometrically similar backgrounds. Similarly, the subtle reflectance differences

between the R_{645} and the band R_{2130} are exploited for the same purpose.

4. Results

The performance of the ECMA algorithm was evaluated across seven MODIS scenes selected to represent a broad range of temporal and geographic variability. These test scenes encompass diverse atmospheric conditions, including varying levels of sun-glint, different aerosol types and loads, as well as heterogeneous land surface characteristics. For each result presented, the corresponding figure reference is provided, wherein labels (a) and (b) denote the ECMA and MCM image outputs, respectively. Each result also includes a statistical

accuracy metric computed for each scene based on the corresponding ECMA and MCM datasets, using a 2×2 contingency table.

4.1. Yellow Sea, Aqua 09 October 2013 (Fig. 6)

According to Shi et al. (2021), this aqua image shows an intense pollution plume over East Asia, which is categorized as a cloud. This agrees with Tan et al. (2018), who found that haze and dust pollution can disturb MODIS cloud detection. The ECMA demonstrated an ability to circumvent the erroneous classification of such pollutants as clouds. Consequently, the level of agreement between it and the MCM stood at a modest 19%.

Figure 6. The resultant image outputs: (a) RGB, (b) ECMA and (c) MYD35 for an Aqua swath over the Yellow Sea, N37° 38' 20" E121° 35' 01", 09 October 2013 at 05:02

4.2. Arabian Sea, Aqua 18 June 2008 (Fig. 7)

A sizable sandstorm, spanning across Afghanistan and Iran and extending from the terrestrial region into the waters of the Arabian Sea, is observable in this imagery. The ECMA effectively distinguished clouds from the dense dust

concentrations both over the land and the sea, with minimal misclassification of aerosol loads. The MCM mischaracterized most of the dust within the scene as clouds, leading to a rather modest concordance rate of 18% when compared to the results obtained by the ECMA.

Figure 7. The resultant image outputs: (a) RGB, (b) ECMA and (c) MYD35 for an Aqua swath over the Arabian Sea, N17° 01' 38" E59° 50' 38", 18 June 2008 at 09:23

4.3. Arabian Sea, Terra 21 December 2011 (Fig. 8)

During this satellite observation, an atypical dust formation with an unusual shape and coloration was detected as it moved from Iran across the landmass toward the Arabian Sea. The MCM predominantly labelled the majority of the “white-colored” dust

plume as cloud cover over both terrestrial and marine regions. By contrast, the ECMA product was less problematic, successfully sidestepping the misclassification of such aerosol particles, thereby achieving an accuracy matching value of 25%.

Figure 8. The resultant image outputs: (a) RGB, (b) ECMA and (c) MOD35 for a Terra swath over the Arabian Sea, N24° 17' 45" E57° 57' 43", 21 December 2011 at 06:56

4.4. Gulf of Oman Terra 27 April 2015 (Fig. 9)

In this dust-free image, there is an evident presence of an irregular circular sun-glint and faint, finely-textured cloud formations. While the MCM misclassified the glints as clouds

and also exhibited an overestimation of thinly-veiled cloud structures, the ECMA successfully averted misclassification within the scene and As a result, the ECMA achieved a notably high accuracy rate of 78%.

Figure 9. The resultant image outputs: (a) RGB, (b) ECMA and (c) MOD35 for a Terra swath over the Gulf of Oman, N24° 17' 45" E57° 57' 43", 27 April 2015 at 06:42

4.5. Philippine Sea, Aqua 05 May 2012 (Fig. 10)

In this MODIS Aqua image, a prominent sun-glint strip is visibly traversing the central region of the swath, extending over the Philippine Sea. The MCM successfully discerned clouds within

the entirety of this glint-affected area, with the exception of a minor segment. Conversely, the ECMA passed the masking evaluation without any erroneous classification within the glint area, resulting in a 75% concurrence rate with the MCM.

Figure 10. The resultant image outputs: (a) RGB, (b) ECMA and (c) MYD35 for an Aqua swath over the Philippine Sea, N24° 52' 35" E134° 40' 44", 05 May 2012 at 04:20

4.6. Baltic Sea, Terra 23 August 2002 (Fig. 11)

In this image, the Baltic Sea appears to be dust-free and glint-free in this image. The ECMA outcomes closely paralleled the

results produced by NASA counterpart in masking nearly all visible clouds within the scene, leading to a concordant agreement rate of 74%.

Figure 11. The resultant image outputs: (a) RGB, (b) ECMA and (c) MYD35 for a Terra swath over the Baltic Sea, N59° 33' 46" E21° 35' 55", 02 August 2002 at 09:37

4.7. Australia, Aqua 23 October 2002 (Fig. 12)

A large, thick layer of iron-based dust storm was observed across eastern Australia. Bushfires smoke plumes can also be seen as white-greyish plumes mixed with dust extending towards the waters over the Tasman Sea circled in Fig. 12 (a) (Mctainsh et al., 2005). ECMA successfully identified all these cloud-

lookalike features as non-cloudy formations, and they were not masked as clouds. The accuracy findings between the ECMA and the equivalent MODIS mask yielded a discrepancy of 27%. This divergence can be attributed to MCM's inability to differentiate dense aerosol concentrations and subsequently categorize them as clouds.

Figure 12. The resultant image outputs: (a) RGB (Fire plumes circled next to a thick dust plume), (b) ECMA and (c) MYD35 for an Aqua swath over Australia, S28° 17' 36" E156° 48' 37", 23 October 2002 at 03:25

MODIS (pixels)	ECMA (pixels)	Presence of sever aerosol (A) or/and severe sun-glint (G)
17800	9467	A
69238	38492	A
38459	6948	A
9081	29531	G
46501	41307	G
18897	44058	—
38292	44761	A

Table 2. Number of pixels masked as cloudy in MODIS and ECMA scenes corresponding to the datasets labeled (a) and (b), respectively, in Figures 6–12.

Table 2 summarizes the masked pixel counts used in the 2×2 contingency tables, from which the accuracy results were derived for the ECMA and MCM images. To assess the concordance between these datasets, a Bland-Altman plot was generated, as depicted in Fig. 13. The graphical representation indicates the absence of discernible systematic bias in the outcomes produced by the two algorithms, as evidenced by the mean differences closely approximating zero. Additionally, a consensus in the efficacy of cloud masking between the ECMA and MCM datasets is observed, particularly in events free from substantial occurrences of heavy aerosols and sun-glint.

Figure 13. A Bland-Altman plot generated using the data presented in Table 2.

5. Conclusions

The empirical cloud mask algorithm (ECMA) is a robust method for producing a simple yes/no decision of day-only clouds viewable in multi-spectral sensors. It uses several spectral mixing operations involving a total of eight bands of MODIS at the 1-km pixel resolution: the five spectral bands (R₄₆₉, R₅₅₅, R₆₄₅, R₈₅₉ and R₂₁₃₀) and two emissive bands (BT₁₁ and BT₁₂). The spectral band mixing operations require no atmospheric correction and uses only Rayleigh-corrected reflectance values. Therefore, it will allow operators of near-real-time datasets to generate accurate initial predictions of day-cloud formations in advance of the accessibility of more intricate and dependable datasets.

A MODIS scene devoid of any significant disturbances, such as sun-glint, mineralogically variable dust, or pollution-related haze or fires, the ECMA mask demonstrated a strong

correspondence with the outcome from the corresponding MCM output. Visual inspection of RGB composites indicated that ECMA and MCM agreed on cloud/no-cloud delineation in roughly 70–80% of observed regions, with typical correspondence around 75% (Fig 13). Using MCM as an operational benchmark suggests that the ECMA approach is broadly reliable and suitable as a proof-of-concept. However, future work should include quantitative, truth-based validation using ground or airborne measurements to establish formal performance metrics.

While the ECMA is grounded in empirical formulation rather than radiative transfer theory, this supports the claims made in the paper. The algorithm was refined through systematic observation across diverse environmental conditions, allowing the spectral terms and nonlinear expressions to be tuned specifically for challenging scenarios such as sun-glint, dust, haze, and mixed land/water boundaries. It demonstrates its correspondence with visually interpreted RGB imagery, showing that the method can suppress persistent sources of misclassification while preserving real cloud structures. Although empirical, the ECMA therefore provides a practical and operationally applicable cloud-masking solution, with its current limitations, as it is the case of snow/ice confusion and reduced night-time applicability, representing clear pathways for improvement in future work and its applicability to datasets produced from other optical sensors.

Conflicts of Interest

The author reports no conflict of interest.

Data and Materials Availability

The data utilized in this study were obtained through public license access from (<https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov>). Data is available from the author upon request.

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